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Research Article

Challenges Encountered by Prospective Teachers During Teaching Practice: A Cross-Sectional Survey of B. Ed (Hons) Level

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 18-Aug-24 Revised: 11-Oct-24 Accepted: 18-Oct-24 Published: 21-Oct-24	This study was conducted to identify the problems faced by the prospective teachers during teaching practice at the B. Ed (Hone) level. The study was descriptive by nature and a survey was conducted to collect the data. There were a total of 134 prospective teachers enrolled in semesters 4 th and 8 th . A universal sampling technique was used to draw the sample from the population. The study was delimited to the University of Kotli AJ&K and Affiliated colleges (Sir Syed College, Guidance College). A five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used in this research. Data were collected personally by the researcher after testing the reliability and validity of the study. The data collected were analyzed by applying frequency, percentage, and mean. It was found that ninety-two percent of prospective teachers agreed that prospective teachers face difficulty in using methods according to the needs of students. Therefore, it is recommended that there be a seminar or workshop before sending the prospective teachers to the schools.
Keywords:	Challenges, Prospective Teachers, Teaching Practice, B. Ed Level
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Introduction

Teaching is the ability to guide someone to improve his knowledge and develop discipline. Teaching as a process improves both the teachers and the students who are learning. The teacher can understand the requirements and interests of each student by practicing teaching. The focus in teaching practice is the learning of students. As a practice of teaching, teachers help students to acquire knowledge, learn new things, build their confidence, and shape their behavior. The role of a teacher is very important in changing the lives of students (Accurso & Gebhard, 2021). Teaching is the art of helping to learn new things. Teaching guides knowledge improvement and discipline of both teachers and students. Teachers understand students' interests, helping them acquire knowledge, build confidence, and shape their behavior.

The process of guiding an individual to learn is known as teaching. It is one of our essential responsibilities. Teaching allows individuals to gain the knowledge and attitudes needed to be responsible citizens, find work, and live peacefully. It also provides a main mechanism for imparting knowledge to the next generation (Jabbarov, 2020). Teaching is a process that supports individuals in developing skills. Individuals can learn to be responsible citizens by learning their rights and obligations as well as the rules and regulations that govern their society, through education.

During teaching practice, under the guidance of an experienced mentor, prospective teachers gain first-hand experience in the classroom teaching environment. The time spent practicing teaching can vary depending on the course and the institution (Orchard & Winch, 2015). Teacher education institutions are committed to generating trained educators capable of providing pupils with high-quality education. This experience is crucial because it allows aspiring teachers to apply knowledge and skills in real-world teaching scenarios. According to Bovill (2020), teaching practice involves a variety of practices that potential teachers engage in a genuine classroom and school setting. Teaching practice may be summed up as the period spent by aspiring teachers working under the guidance of a mentor teacher to gain experience in the classroom. Teaching practice means a few activities that prospective teachers engage in a real classroom and school setting. Like lesson planning, classroom management, student assessment, etc. The mentor teacher gives the prospective teachers comments, support, and advice, assisting them in developing their teaching skills and becoming more successful educators.

Teaching practice is necessary for prospective teachers for a variety of reasons. At the first stage, it allows the learner to put into practice what he has learned in his teacher training. It covers everything from lesson planning, and delivering to class and evaluation management. It also enables him to try out different teaching strategies and approaches to see what works best for him and his students for teaching. Second, teaching practice gives valuable experience dealing with actual students in a real classroom environment. It can be a very different experience when working with children in other environments. He will meet administrators, education professionals, and other teachers who can provide crucial advice and support as he begins his career. These connections can be helpful as he looks for jobs, apply for positions, and advance in his career (Sepulveda-Escobar & Morrison, 2020).

According to Azeem (2011), Almost everywhere in the world, schools of education have been founded to provide professional education for teachers. Teacher education in Pakistan is implemented at different levels of education. Bachelor of Education (B. Ed) and Master of Education (M. Ed) programs have been taught at different colleges and universities. Prospective teachers get instruction in a variety of areas from teachers' training institutes, in addition to theoretical knowledge and expertise. Teacher training institutions are becoming increasingly

important in today's society, as the quality of education is closely related to the quality of teachers. Colleges and Universities all around the world have built teacher training programs that not only transmit theoretical information but also practical understanding in various subjects.

Prospective teacher training is very essential for pre-service teachers. In Pakistan, secondary-level teacher training plays an important role. The B. Ed programs prepare quality teachers to improve the quality of school education and enhance the learning level of students. In this direction, many efforts were made to implement the various recommendations made by different commissions and committees in Pakistan. In 1978, 1988, and 2009, the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) also brought out national curriculum frameworks for teacher education therefore, recommended improving the quality of preprograms. The Justice Verma Commission (2012) recommended that the B. Ed program should be two years along with adequate provision to branch out into specializations in curriculum studies, policy, finance, and foundational studies (Kalloo et al., 2020).

NCTE has decided to convert the one-year courses of the B. Ed programs into two-year courses from 2015 onwards throughout the country. Because B. Ed is a professional course, expertise and strategies are more important than the extensive theoretical framework of the curriculum. The two-year B. Ed programs, recommended by NCTE, 2014 can prepare quality teachers and fulfill the needs of the students. Against this backdrop, the problem faced by prospective teachers after the two-year B. Ed programs must be known. It is this feeling that has urged the investigator to take up the present study entitled, "Problems faced by the prospective teachers during two-year B. Ed level. It is expected that this study, through small, prospective teachers can make some significant contributions in the field of education. In the field of education programs, prospective teachers face numerous problems like academic problems, cooperative teacher-related problems, managing a heavy workload, and transport issues (Manna & Jayanta, 2016).

Kaldi & Xafakos (2017), research to determine the reasons faced by prospective teachers during teaching practice. Why supervisors do not organize regular meetings with prospective teachers, why they do not receive adequate encouragement, and why do administrative teachers have a bad attitude toward them? The researcher faced financial problems and transportation problems during the teaching practice. During teaching practice, researchers faced problems in adopting teaching methodologies according to the needs of students due to lack of experience. The researcher personally faced all these problems that are why the researcher selected this topic to identify other problems faced by prospective teachers during teaching at the B. Ed (Hons) level in Kotli AJ&K. Therefore, the current study is an attempt to fulfill this gap.

Review of Related Literature

Teaching Practice

Arrington (2023) claims that the phrase "teaching practice" refers to the variety of experiences that aspiring educators encounter when working in classrooms and educational institutions. Teaching practice, according to Loose and Ryan (2020), is a supervised teaching experience in which aspiring teachers take on more responsibility for guiding a group's learning over time. Future educators benefit much from teaching practice since it exposes them to a range of classroom and school settings. It gives them practical experience by enabling them to use their knowledge and abilities in a real-world situation.

The process of preparing aspiring teachers for teaching through hands-on instruction is known as teaching practice. It involves using instructional methods, principles, and tactics in a

practical way as well as practicing various aspects of everyday school life (Gujjar et al., 2010). In order to close the knowledge gap between theory and classroom experience, teaching practice is essential. It is a crucial part of teacher education programs because it enables skill development, classroom management, and adaptation to a variety of learners.

To obtain teaching experience, aspiring teachers are assigned to schools for teaching practice. By fully integrating them into the school environment, teaching practice aims to prepare aspiring educators for their future careers by giving them a sense of belonging and allowing them to reflect on the realities of teaching in a classroom (Mannathoko, 2013). Teaching practice aims to integrate future teachers into school environments by providing real-world experience, understanding school culture, observing experienced educators, adapting to classroom challenges, building confidence, and connecting theoretical knowledge to practical teaching.

According to Brandt *et al.*, (2019), Teaching practice allows students to: a) use the information and abilities gained in the teacher education work course. b) Describe an attitude that is congruent with successful teaching. b) Using a variety of learning concepts and instructional methodologies. b) recognizing the roles of educators. e) Exhibit rudimentary competence in all areas of instructional functions. g) Provide evidence for moral and professional conduct. Teaching practice gives aspiring educators a better understanding of the real teaching world and informs them of potential issues and challenges. Therefore, aspiring educators need to be aware of the surroundings of their students and embrace their differences. Additionally, teaching practice helps aspiring educators move from being students to being new teachers (Koross, 2016). In addition to building problem-solving skills, teaching practice exposes aspiring educators to scheduling and responsibility issues, giving them practical experience and insight into potential career obstacles.

Problems Faced by Prospective Teachers During Teaching Practice

Teaching practice is a challenging but essential part of teacher education, especially in poor nations, according to Meirovitz et al. (2022). Prospective teachers in poor nations faced a variety of challenges during their teaching practicum. Prospective teachers encounter obstacles during the teaching practice program, including lack of preparation, geographic distance, low teacher expertise, lack of resources, lack of discipline among a diverse group of students and educators, lack of financial facilities, lack of support, and lack of trust from cooperating teachers.

Supervisors do not regularly meet with aspiring teachers to talk about the difficulties they encounter when practicing their teaching, according to Lorensius et al. (2022). Additionally, academic supervisors do not adequately support aspiring teachers in their work, they do not receive sufficient help from their cooperating teachers in acquiring textbooks and teacher guides, they do not receive sufficient explanations of the necessary skills, and they do not receive sufficient guidance to inspire them to carry out classroom activities. Issues that prospective teachers encounter include poor preparation, a lack of experience, a lack of resources, a lack of discipline, a lack of funding, and accommodations, and a lack of interest in school activities.

According to Meyer *et al.*, (2019), the difficulties addressed by the prospective teachers during teaching practice in South Africa indicate that most supervisors of teaching practice are unaware of their responsibilities as mentors to prospective teachers during teaching practice. Supervisors see their responsibility as being a university assignment to supervise. The study in South Africa found that most supervisors of teaching practice are not well-informed about their responsibilities as teaching practice mentors, viewing their duties as university assignments.

Lack of Resources

Resources are critical for effective teaching and learning in the classroom. In the lack of

resources, students get frustrated, and this makes their teaching practice a difficult task. The role of resources in facilitating effective teaching practice and creating a conducive learning environment in the classroom is critical. It can be difficult for teachers to engage students and provide them with the necessary learning tools when resources are limited. This can lead to student anxiety, making teaching a more difficult task (DACANAY *et al.*, 2019). Limited resources can hinder effective teaching practices and create a challenging learning environment, potentially leading to student anxiety and increased difficulty in teaching.

There are still schools in South Africa without libraries and with an extremely limited supply of textbooks. There are still students who swap textbooks in class. This is a challenging duty for aspiring teachers since it entails issues of classroom administration and control, as well as the discipline of students. Some schools are still having problems with photocopying and this process is when prospective teachers create classes and other support material for learners for evaluation and homework (Chang, 2013). South Africa still lacks libraries and a significant textbook shortage, posing challenges for teachers in classroom management and discipline.

The school should help prospective teachers in developing a system that supports greater learning possibilities, a system in which students see themselves as benefactors of classroom discipline instead of victims of it. This demands a careful and methodical approach to school discipline, intending to identify and prevent or eliminate probable causes (Foncha *et al.*, 2015). The schools may support teachers in creating a learning system where learners view classroom discipline as a benefit rather than a victim, systematically addressing potential causes.

Coordination of School Timetable with University Timetable

It is difficult for students to balance their schedules between school and university. They work at school until 8 a.m., then attend university classes. It is extremely difficult for prospective teachers to manage time and coordinate with school and university schedules. (Kim *et al.*, 2022). Balancing school and university schedules is challenging for students, who work until 8 a.m., and for prospective teachers, managing time and coordinating with both schedules is challenging.

According to Pelikan *et al.*, (2021), The importance of lesson planning and its associated issues. Some of the challenges that must be addressed are teaching techniques, time management, class delivery, and identifying educational objectives. According to König *et al.*, (2020), teachers have limited time for course design due to the problems that prospective teachers face throughout their practical teaching period, such as short length. Teachers are unable to master new skills or build new teaching methodologies if their time is rigorously split or constrained by a lot of lessons. Prospective teachers' coordinate their timetable by working with their university and their school to ensure that they can meet the requirements of both programs. They may need to communicate with their university to determine when their courses and other requirements are scheduled, and then work with their school to determine when they will be teaching (Keiler, 2018).

Prospective teachers may also need to be flexible and willing to adjust their schedules as needed to accommodate changes in their university or school timetable. This cooperation is essential because it ensures that prospective teachers can satisfy the criteria of both programs while also gaining the experience and knowledge required to be great teachers (Girvan *et al.*, 2016). Prospective teachers must coordinate their timetable with their university and school to meet program requirements. They must communicate with their university to schedule courses and work with their school to schedule teaching. Flexibility is crucial for gaining the experience and knowledge needed for success in teaching.

Managing Heavy Workload

Due to university classes and training, there is a heavy workload on prospective teachers.

It is difficult for them to manage the workload either they focus on their study, or they handle their training in a good way by managing classes and their courses. The first experience is difficult for prospective teachers to face challenges during training (Wanner & Palmer, 2015). Prospective teachers face heavy workloads due to university classes and training, making it difficult to manage their studies or effectively manage classes and courses during their first experience.

Teaching is a multitasking activity. Prospective teachers must set aside time to prepare lesson plans and teaching aids, as well as assess the work assigned to them as homework in class. All of these activities wear them out. Some prospective teachers who are unable to cope with the mental strain often consider quitting their studies. Mental and emotional stress is also felt when teachers' supervisors or their own lecturers write negative comments on their record books (Weldon *et al.*, 2021). Teaching is a multitasking activity, requiring preparation, assessment, and evaluation. Mental strain can lead to quitting studies. Negative feedback from supervisors or lecturers can further exacerbate the stress.

When they feel like they can't handle a certain duty, like teaching a disruptive class, prospective instructors may experience anxiety. For aspiring teachers, creating charts and models takes a lot of time. While the school laboratory can assist some science students, others find it to be a daily burden at home (Tum, 2015). When faced with difficult and time-consuming duties, such as managing disruptive classrooms or creating charts and models, prospective instructors may become anxious.

Harsh Attitude of Teachers with Prospective Teachers

Harsh attitude of teachers towards prospective teachers during teaching practice; they are being excessively strict, critical, or unkind in their interactions and feedback. Instead of providing constructive guidance and support, they may be overly harsh, which can create a negative and discouraging experience for aspiring teachers. This can make prospective teachers feel bad and less motivated to learn (Fatima & Malik, 2015). Teachers' harsh attitudes towards prospective teachers during teaching practice can create a negative experience, discouraging them and reducing their motivation to learn.

Teachers who are supposed to help and mentor prospective teachers are being too tough and unfavorable, making it difficult for prospective teachers to learn and grow comfortably. This kind of behavior can be discouraging and may hinder the development of the prospective teacher's skills and confidence in the classroom. Teachers should strive to be patient, understanding, and encouraging, helping prospective teachers improve their teaching abilities in a positive and nurturing environment (Robinson, 2014). Teachers' unfavorable behavior towards prospective teachers can hinder their growth and development. To foster a positive environment, they should be patient, understanding, and encouraging, promoting a nurturing environment.

Misbehave of Students with Prospective Teachers

Students may misbehave with a new prospective teacher because they think of them as a temporary or unfamiliar figure in the classroom. They might put the constraints to the test to observe how the new teacher behaves. To earn the respect of their students and create a positive learning environment, prospective teachers must establish clear boundaries and expectations from the beginning (Ladson-Billings, 2018). Students may misbehave with new teachers if they think of them as prospective teachers are temporary. However prospective teachers create a positive learning environment, and clear boundaries and expectations must be established from the start. As a prospective teacher, you may be perceived as having less authority compared to experienced teachers. Students might benefit from this perceived lack of authority to engage in disruptive behavior. Some students may feel unsure or uncomfortable with changes in their classroom

dynamics. Misbehavior can be a way for them to manage their uncertainty or anxiety (Buchs *et al.*, 2017). Prospective teachers may be perceived as less authoritative than experienced ones, leading to disruptive behavior among students who feel unsure or uncomfortable with classroom changes.

Misbehavior of students with prospective teachers during teaching practice can arise due to various reasons. Some students may be acting out due to a lack of discipline in the classroom. Others may be bored or disengaged with the lesson, leading them to act out to get attention or to avoid participating in the lesson. Some students may be dealing with personal issues that are causing them to act out in class. Prospective teachers need to understand these underlying issues and work to tackle them to create a positive learning environment (Debreli & Ishanova, 2019).

Lack of Teaching and Learning Material in the Classroom

According to Emre (2019), the lack of teaching and learning material in the classroom during teaching practice can represent numerous challenges for prospective teachers. Teaching material is a necessary source that supports the learning process and helps create engaging and effective lessons. When they are lacking, the following issues may arise limited engagement, difficulty addressing different learning styles, inability to demonstrate concepts, strain on creativity, and impact on teacher confidence. Lack of teaching materials in classrooms can pose challenges for teachers, including limited engagement, difficulty addressing learning styles, inability to demonstrate concepts, strain on creativity, and impacting teacher confidence.

Limited Engagement

It can be difficult to capture students' attention and maintain their interest in the lesson without visual aids, hands-on activities, or additional material. This lack of engagement can lead to student disengagement and decreased participation. Using interactive and stimulating teaching techniques can help keep students engaged and improve their learning experience. To foster a positive and inclusive classroom environment, it is critical to make the lessons dynamic and engaging (Kalyani & Rajasekaran, 2018). Using interactive teaching techniques and visual aids can enhance student engagement and participation, fostering a positive and inclusive classroom environment by ensuring dynamic and stimulating lessons.

Research Objectives

1. To identify the problems faced by the prospective teachers during teaching practice at B. Ed level.
2. To find out the personal related problems faced by prospective teachers during teaching practice.

Research Methodology

This study was descriptive and the survey method was used to identify the problems faced by the prospective teachers during teaching practice at the B. Ed level. All the students at the University of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Affiliated colleges (Sir Syed College and Guidance College) semesters 4th and 8th at B. Ed level constitute the population of the study which is 134. All the prospective teachers who are engaged in teaching practice are included in the sample (4th and 8th). The universal sampling technique was used by the researcher, and the whole population was selected as the sample of the study due to the small population. The researcher prepared a Five-Point Likert Scale questionnaire as a research instrument to collect the data from students of semesters 4th and 8th at B. Ed level. The questionnaire was used to identify the problems faced by the prospective teachers during teaching practice at the B. Ed level. There were 34 statements in

the questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by four educational experts of the Department of Education University of Kotli AJ&K. Using a pilot study, the researcher distributed a questionnaire among 20 prospective teachers who were the part of population but not be part of the sample. The reliability of the instrument was checked by the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The reliability of the instrument was 0.80 which was acceptable for further research. Moreover, the data were collected personally by visiting the University of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir and affiliated colleges (Sir Syed College, Guidance College). Data were analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The researcher used simple mean, frequency, and percentage for the analysis of data.

Results

Table 1

Mean analysis of a personal problem

Statements	N	Mean
Perspective teachers face difficulty in time management during classes	134	3.79
Prospective teachers face students' behavior problems	134	3.72
Despite the workload, prospective teachers pay full attention in the study	134	3.51
Prospective teachers face difficulty in using methods according to the needs of students	134	3.75
Prospective teachers face difficulty in teaching some subject	134	3.83
Prospective teachers face difficulty in getting transportation	134	3.76

Table 1 shows the mean scores of personal problems. The table further shows that the mean score of Perspective teachers face difficulty in time management during classes; N= 134, M=3.79, Prospective teachers face students' behavior problems; N= 134, M= 3.72, Despite workload, prospective teachers pay full attention in study; N=134, M=3.51, Prospective teachers face difficulty in using methods according to the needs of students; N=134, M=3.75, Prospective teachers face difficulty to teach some subject; N=134, M=3.83, and Prospective teachers face difficulty in getting transportation; N=134, M=3.76. Furthermore, the results directed that Prospective teachers who face difficulty in teaching some subject has the highest mean score in personal problems.

Table 2

Mean Analysis of Academic/Professional Problems

Statements	N	Mean
Prospective teachers face difficulties in balancing responsibilities during strict schedules of teaching practice	134	3.85
Prospective teachers face difficulty in the implementation of teaching methods during teaching practice	134	3.64
Prospective teachers may face difficulties in motivating students	134	3.27
Prospective teachers face difficulties in managing parental expectations	134	3.80

Prospective teachers face difficulty in paying full attention to their studies	134	3.31
Prospective teachers face difficulty in balancing group learning activities during teaching practice	134	3.52

Table 2 shows the mean scores of academic problems. The table further shows that the mean score of Prospective teachers face difficulties in balancing multi-responsibilities during strict schedule of teaching practice; N= 134, M=3.85, Prospective teachers face difficulty in implementation of teaching methods during teaching practice; N= 134, M= 3.64, Prospective teachers may face difficulties in motivating students; N=134, M=3.27, Prospective teachers face difficulties in managing parental expectations; N=134, M=3.80, Prospective teachers face difficulty to pay full attention to their studies; N=134, M=3.31, and Prospective teachers face difficulty in balancing group learning activities during teaching practice; N=134, M=3.52. Furthermore, the results directed that Prospective teachers who face difficulties in balancing responsibilities during strict schedules of teaching practice has the highest mean score in academic problems.

Table 3
Mean analysis of Problems related to cooperative teacher

Statements	N	Mean
The rudeness of the Cooperative teacher makes prospective teachers tense during lesson delivery	134	3.83
Co-operative teacher gives harsh comments about prospective teacher performance	134	3.26
Co-operative teacher gives improper feedback on prospective teachers' work	134	3.59
Prospective teachers fall favoritism from Co-operative teacher	134	3.38
Co-operative teachers stay at a distance from prospective teachers	134	3.42
Co-operative teacher takes more work from prospective teachers	134	3.63

Table 3 shows the mean scores of problems related to cooperative teachers. The table further represented that The rudeness of Co-operative teacher makes prospective teachers tense during lesson delivery; N= 134, M=3.83, Co-operative teacher gives harsh comments about prospective teacher performance; N= 134, M= 3.26, Co-operative teacher gives improper feedback on prospective teachers work; N=134, M=3.59, Prospective teachers fall favoritism from Co-operative teacher; N=134, M=3.38, Co-operative teacher stays at distance from prospective teachers; N=134, M=3.42, and Co-operative teacher takes more work from prospective teachers; N=134, M=3.63. Furthermore, the results directed that The rudeness of Co-operative teachers makes prospective teachers tense during lesson delivery and has the highest mean score in problems related to cooperative teachers.

Table 4
Mean analysis of head teacher-related problems

Statements	N	Mean
Co-operative teacher takes more work from prospective teachers	134	3.83
Head-Teacher involves prospective teachers in Parents Teacher Meetings (PTM)	134	3.49

The headteacher gives prospective teachers the proper timetable to teach the classes	134	3.54
Head-Teacher involves prospective teachers in extra-curricular activities	134	3.35
Head-Teacher monitors the classes regularly.	134	3.45
Head-Teacher accepts the prospective teachers as a teacher	134	3.44

Table 4 shows the mean scores of head teacher-related problems. The table further represented that Co-operative teacher takes more work from prospective teachers; N= 134, M=3.83, Head-Teacher involves prospective teachers in Parents Teacher Meeting (PTM); N= 134, M= 3.49, Head-Teacher gives prospective teachers proper timetable to teach the classes; N=134, M=3.54, Head-Teacher involves prospective teachers in extra-curricular activities; N=134, M=3.35, Head-Teacher monitors the classes regularly; N=134, M=3.45, and Head-Teacher accepts the prospective teachers as a teacher; N=134, M=3.44. Furthermore, the results directed that Cooperative teacher takes more work from prospective teachers has the highest mean score in head teacher-related problems.

Table 5

Mean analysis of university and school related other problems

Statements	N	Mean
School staff provides proper arrangements for sitting in the school	134	3.82
School staff shows a cooperative attitude toward prospective teachers	134	3.50
Prospective teachers face difficulty in preparing material for a successful lesson	134	3.63
Prospective teachers feel anxiety due to workload	134	3.53
Regular teachers assign their teaching workload to prospective teachers.	134	3.54
Prospective teachers face difficulty in the formulation of specific objectives of the topic	134	3.52
Prospective teachers face difficulty in developing the previous knowledge testing	134	3.50
Prospective teachers face difficulty in managing large classes	134	3.70
Despite limited time, prospective teachers teach students properly	134	3.43

Table 5 shows the mean scores of university and school-related problems. The table further represented that School staff provides a proper arrangement for sitting in the school; N= 134, M=3.82 School staff shows a cooperative attitude towards prospective teachers; N= 134, M= 3.50, Prospective teachers face difficulty in preparing material for a successful lesson; N=134, M=3.63, Prospective teachers feel anxiety due to workload; N=134, M=3.53, Regular teachers assign their teaching workload to prospective teachers; N=134, M=3.54, Prospective teachers face difficulty in formulation of specific objectives of the topic; N=134, M=3.52, Prospective teachers face difficulty in developing the previous knowledge testing; N=134, M=3.50, Prospective teachers face difficulty in managing large classes; N=134, M=3.70, Prospective teachers face difficulty in managing large classes; N=134, M=3.70 and Despite limited time, prospective teachers teach students properly; N=134, M=3.43. Furthermore, the results directed that School staff providing proper arrangements for sitting in the school has the highest mean score in university and school-related problems.

Discussion

Prospective teachers encounter numerous challenges during their teaching practice, which impact their effectiveness in the classroom and contribute to stress. Time management is a significant issue, as these teachers often struggle to balance lesson preparation with classroom delivery. The added challenge of managing student behavior can exacerbate this problem, especially since many prospective teachers have not yet developed the necessary skills to address diverse student needs effectively. Moreover, the workload, particularly in large classes, can be overwhelming, leading to high levels of stress. Research has shown that workload stress, especially for novice educators, is a key factor contributing to teacher burnout (Klassen & Chiu, 2011).

In addition to workload and time management issues, prospective teachers face difficulties in balancing their teaching responsibilities with their academic studies. This balancing act can lead to reduced focus on their own learning, which affects their academic performance (Tadesse & Tesfay, 2020). Furthermore, implementing teaching methods that cater to individual student needs requires both flexibility and experience, something new teachers are still developing. This can lead to frustration when they are unable to meet the varying needs of their students effectively.

Another significant challenge comes from the interactions with cooperative teachers. Harsh feedback, favoritism, and a lack of constructive guidance can make prospective teachers feel tense and unsupported during lesson delivery. Research underscores the importance of supportive mentorship in teacher education, where unsupportive behaviors from cooperating teachers—such as assigning extra work or giving improper feedback—can diminish the learning opportunities for prospective teachers (Hudson, 2010).

The role of head teachers also influences the teaching experience. When head teachers adopt an autocratic style and assign prospective teachers additional responsibilities—such as organizing Parent Teacher Meetings or involving them in extracurricular activities—this can further burden the teachers. Studies suggest that effective leadership from head teachers should involve a balance between providing guidance and respecting the professional boundaries of prospective teachers (Hallinger, 2011). However, when head teachers overburden these teachers, it can contribute to feelings of stress and inadequacy.

Although some schools provide logistical support, such as seating arrangements and cooperative staff, prospective teachers still face challenges in preparing lesson materials and managing their workload. Regular teachers may sometimes assign their own teaching responsibilities to prospective teachers, adding to their stress and workload. Anxiety caused by these pressures can hinder the performance and development of prospective teachers. Research has long emphasized the negative effects of stress on teacher well-being, particularly during the early stages of their careers (Kyriacou, 2001).

Managing large classes is another challenge faced by prospective teachers, especially when time is limited. Large class sizes reduce the ability of teachers to provide individual attention, which is crucial for effective learning. Prospective teachers often lack the experience required to manage large groups of students while maintaining engagement and discipline, leading to decreased confidence and effectiveness in the classroom (Blatchford et al., 2011). These

difficulties, combined with the time constraints of teaching practice, create an environment where prospective teachers struggle to meet expectations.

Conclusions

1. Prospective teachers face difficulty in time management during classes, student behavior problems, teaching methods used according to the needs of students, financial problems, workload, difficulty in teaching some subjects, and also difficulty in getting transportation.
2. Prospective teachers face difficulties in balancing responsibilities, implementing teaching methods, motivating students, managing parental expectations, face difficulty to pay full attention to their studies, and also face difficulty in balancing group learning activities during teaching practice.
3. The rudeness of cooperative teachers makes prospective teachers tense during lesson delivery, harsh comments, improper feedback, favoritism, staying at a distance, and also face difficulties taking more work from prospective teachers.
4. The Auto-creative style of the head teacher is common for the prospective teacher head-teacher to involve prospective teachers in Parents Teacher Meetings, give to proper timetable to teach the classes, involved in extracurricular activities, monitor the classes regularly, and also face difficulties the head- teacher accepts the prospective teachers as a teacher.
5. School staff provides proper arrangements for sitting in school, school staff show a cooperative attitude, and also face difficulty in preparing material for a successful lesson. Prospective teachers feel anxiety, about workload, regular teachers assign their teaching workload to prospective teachers, and face difficulty in the formulation of specific objectives of the topic.
6. Prospective teachers face difficulty in developing the previous knowledge testing, and managing large classes and also face difficulty despite limited time, prospective teachers teach students properly.

Recommendations

1. Prospective teachers create daily schedules, this helps the prospective teachers to allocate time for different activities and ensure that everything gets done. There may be a seminar and workshops before sending the prospective teachers, proper orientations must be done, and prospective teachers may be provided practical training in a variety of teaching methods based on the requirements of their students.
2. The potential instructors may receive some financial assistance from higher authorities to maintain them while they are practicing teaching. For aspiring teachers, competent authorities can set up appropriate transportation so they can practice teaching without any problems.
3. Teaching practice days may be short. Teaching practice may be only in the 4th and 8th semesters of the B. Ed program. HEC may be minimizing teaching practice sessions.
4. To enable them to utilize instructional materials in accordance with their demands, prospective teachers may offer the newest technology and materials, such as digital whiteboards and projectors. The administration may be careful to include guidelines on how to use instructional materials for this reason.
5. Depending on their schedule requirements, the school management may create distinct timetables for aspiring teachers. The management and personnel of the school include the

aspiring teachers in school-related activities. In addition to being permitted to use the facilities and receive practical training for lesson planning beforehand, school cooperative instructors can offer appropriate guidelines for brainstorming and various activities that connect to prior knowledge and brainstorming.

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